

Atomic-Scale Tracing of Lithium Trapped in Copper Current Collectors

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Abstract

Zero-excess lithium-metal batteries (LMBs) are expected to provide the maximum energy density in combination with classic lithium-containing cathode materials. However, the lithium plating process on a blank current collector suffers from huge irreversibility, thus, causing rapid capacity fading. Herein, we employ atom probe tomography to track the occurring lithium losses. The results unambiguously reveal that lithium is initially trapped at grain boundaries and junctions in the copper foil – not only on the copper foil as commonly assumed – with a local concentration up to ~28 at.% at the boundary junctions. Moreover, after continuous plating and stripping, the copper foil sub-surface regions (~100 nm) become nanocrystalline, creating additional defects. These defects promote the diffusion of oxygen and carbon, further favoring lithium trapping in the copper foil sub-surface region. Such compositional and structural changes of the copper foil surface directly contribute to the degradation of the current collector during cycling, which has so far been largely overlooked in discussions of LMB performance decay.

ToC

Does lithium diffuse into the copper current collector during cycling in lithium-metal batteries? This study unveils, at the atomic scale, that lithium is trapped at grain boundaries and junctions – already after only one plating/stripping cycle. After three cycles, the copper foil surface becomes nanocrystalline and oxidized. The resulting defects further trap lithium and oxygen in the subsurface region, thereby degrading the copper current collector.

1. INTRODUCTION

Lithium-metal batteries (LMBs) are considered the next big step forward towards the development of higher energy density batteries, owing to the very low redox potential of -3.04 V vs. the standard hydrogen electrode and its exceptionally high theoretical specific capacity of 3860 mAh g⁻¹.^[1-3] For this reason, lithium-metal negative electrodes have long been regarded as the “holy grail” for next-generation batteries.^[4,5] However, the high reactivity of lithium metal with essentially any of the commonly used electrolytes and the remaining risk of dendritic lithium deposition still hamper its widespread commercial application.^[1,6,7] In this context, “zero-excess” (also called “anode-free”) LMBs, in which lithium from the positive electrode is essentially simply plated on a “blank” current collector upon charge, have recently attracted rapidly increasing interest, as these promise even higher energy densities and substantial cost reduction, as there is no need to handle and process highly reactive lithium-metal foil.^[8-12]

The most studied current collector in “zero-excess” LMBs is copper foil. The choice of copper originates from the commonly accepted consideration that copper is inert in contact with metallic lithium at such low potentials.^[13-16] However, only very few studies have investigated this in more detail, finding that there is, in fact, an irreversible “trapping” of lithium in copper using characterization techniques such as inductively coupled plasma – atomic emission spectroscopy,^[17] neutron depth profiling (NDP),^[18] and time-of-flight secondary mass spectrometry.^[19] The amount of lithium being irreversibly trapped inside the copper foil, however, varies quite significantly between these studies, ranging from 4 µg cm⁻² to 10 µg cm⁻²;^[17,18] with the former value being obtained after electrochemical lithium plating on copper.

Essentially, lithium trapping sites remain rather elusive. It has been proposed by molecular dynamics simulations that lithium might preferably enter the grain boundaries in polycrystalline copper foils, while an *ex situ* X-ray diffraction analysis did not reveal any detectable changes of the crystal structure of the copper foil.^[20] Rupp *et al.*,^[19] though, reported that there is also lithium diffusion into the bulk copper foil when comparing the impact of (i) bringing lithium in direct contact with copper, (ii) polarizing the copper foil in contact with a lithium salt containing electrolyte, and (iii) high-energy lithium implantation – for polycrystalline and single-crystalline copper foils. Nevertheless, a clear experimental proof of the position and distribution of lithium inside copper metal foils as well as a precise quantification, excluding any contribution of lithium-containing electrolyte decomposition products, is missing in the literature, since the so-far used techniques lack sufficiently high spatial resolution and compositional analytical capabilities. Therefore, new characterization tools that are able to provide nanoscopic elemental and compositional details at local regions, such as grain boundaries, are needed to trace lithium trapped in the copper foil.

Atom probe tomography (APT) can provide three-dimensional (3D) spatial distribution and composition data for both light and heavy elements in solid materials, with parts-per-million chemical sensitivity at a sub-nanometer spatial resolution.^[21] Herein, we employ APT to trace where lithium is trapped and its concentration at local regions after one and three plating/stripping cycles in a Li||Cu cell using an ionic liquid-based electrolyte. The aim of this study is to elucidate the lithium trapping sites in the copper foils after the first few cycles. In addition, scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) and transmission Kikuchi diffraction (TKD) were combined with APT to investigate the microstructural changes of the copper foil. To corroborate these atomistic observations, depth-resolved X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was

also employed to complement the determination of the chemical state of the trapped species and the evolution of the solid electrolyte interphase (SEI). We found that lithium is initially trapped at the grain boundaries and boundary junctions after one plating/stripping cycle. Surprisingly, after only two more plating/stripping cycles the copper foil surface becomes nanocrystalline and oxidized, and the newly formed defects and oxygen further trap lithium in the sub-surface region.

2. Results and Discussion

For investigating the potential lithium trapping in a copper current collector, we assembled Li||Cu pouch cells (Illustration of stripping plating process shown in **Figure 1A**) employing a proven electrolyte composed of a mixture of 1-butyl-1-methyl pyrrolidinium bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide (PYR₁₄FSI) and lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide salt (LiTFSI) with a ratio of 8:2 (PYR₁₄FSI:LiTFSI) and 5 wt.% of fluoroethylene carbonate (FEC).^[22] These cells were subjected to either one or three lithium plating and stripping cycles to unveil any impact of the plating and stripping process on the surface of the copper current collector (cf. the schematic illustration in **Figure 1B**). The corresponding plating/stripping profiles are displayed in **Figure 1C,D**, revealing the expected shape. The plating step can be divided into three characteristic regimes, as indicated in the inset of **Figure 1C**. In *Regime 1* (in red), the cell voltage drops steeply as soon as a current is applied. The (very minor) non-linearity can be assigned to electrolyte decomposition, resulting (in part) in the formation of a “solid electrolyte interphase” (SEI) – more precisely maybe in this context, in a (partially) passivating surface layer composed of electrolyte decomposition products. Subsequently, in *Regime 2* (in blue), lithium metal is nucleating on the Cu foil, forming lithium metal deposits, which is accompanied by the

nucleation overpotential. In *Regime 3* (in black), the cell voltage shows a plateau, which is related to the lithium plating on the Cu electrode.^[22–24] The plating/stripping efficiency, i.e., the coulombic efficiency is about 66% for the first plating/stripping cycle and increases to around 85% for the following two cycles, revealing a large irreversibility in the first cycle and still a substantial irreversibility in the following cycles, which is commonly assigned to the aforementioned electrolyte decomposition and the formation of “dead lithium”, i.e., lithium which is for some reason not accessible anymore upon further plating and stripping.^[25,26]

After one or three plating/stripping cycles, the Li||Cu pouch cells were disassembled in an argon-filled glovebox – along with a non-cycled Li||Cu pouch cell serving as reference. The non-cycled and cycled copper foils were rinsed five times with 1,2-dimethoxyethane to remove residual electrolyte. Subsequently, the copper foils were transferred *via* a high-vacuum transfer suitcase to a scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with a focused ion beam (FIB) for TEM and APT specimen preparation. Transferring the as-cleaned copper foils under high vacuum conditions between the glovebox, FIB/SEM and APT is essential for ensuring a precise characterization of their ‘native’ state by APT and scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM in FIB/SEM), since metallic lithium and electrolyte decomposition products can be maintained in their “as-formed” state on the surface of the copper current collector foils. They are highly reactive towards the ambient atmosphere. Also, blank copper is readily oxidized in air when the native passivation layer is removed during cycling (e.g., as a result of the reaction with lithium upon plating). The SEM micrographs in **Figure 2A,B**, i.e., the top-down views of the copper foils, reveal that electrolyte decomposition products are still present on the surface after rinsing (cf. the pristine copper foil surface depicted in **Figure S1**). The electrolyte decomposition

product has a thickness of a few hundred nanometers (see **Figure 2C**, recorded from a TEM lamella showing the cross-section view of the one-cycle copper foil, prepared from the red rectangular region in **Figure 2A**). *Ex situ* XPS depth profiling analysis shows that the SEI layer is generally composed of an organic, i.e., C/O-rich outer layer and an inorganic-rich, e.g., Li₂O and LiF, inner layer (see **Figure S2** along with the detailed discussion of the findings in the Supporting Information), in good agreement with previous studies.^[6] The formation of such electrolyte decomposition products contributes to the initial capacity loss and the rather low coulombic efficiency.

After three plating/stripping cycles, electrolyte decomposition products are present in the form of isolated particles on the copper foil surface (in dark contrast in **Figure 2D** and brighter contrast in **Figure 2B**). The *ex situ* XPS depth profiling analysis reveals a similar organic-to-inorganic stratification (**Figure S3**). With an increased sputtering depth, the SEI again evolves towards an inorganic-rich composition with increasing contributions from LiF and Li₂O. Notably, metallic lithium (Li 1s at ~52.5 eV)^[27] is detected throughout the depth profile, though, with an increasing intensity towards the buried interface, suggesting the formation of “dead” lithium inside the SEI and/or providing a first indication for a “Li trapping” phenomenon inside the near-surface region of the copper current collector.

Remarkably, as first observation, the inset of the STEM image of the three-cycle sample, **Figure 2D**, reveals that the copper foil surface appears ruptured compared to that after one cycle (inset in **Figure 2C**). To further investigate the microstructural changes in the copper foil, TKD was performed on the same TEM lamellae. TKD provides electron backscatter diffraction data with enhanced spatial resolution, revealing grain orientations.^[28] The orientation contrast map in **Figure 2F** shows that the top surface regions of the three-cycle copper foil contain more nanocrystals than

those after one cycle (**Figure 2E**). Taking a closer look at the copper foil surfaces by STEM, we clearly see from **Figure 2H** that the copper foil surface becomes nanocrystalline, with nanograins of ~20 nm in thickness forming in the top ~100 nm sub-surface regions. In comparison, the one-cycle copper foil surface is relatively smooth and flat, and no nanocrystals were observed (**Figure 2G**). Our TKD and STEM images (**Figure 2E-H**) unambiguously show that the grain size on the copper foil surfaces decreases from micrometer-sized grains to nanocrystals as the number of cycles increases. Notably, the copper foil was subjected to only three plating/stripping cycles – not hundreds or even thousands, as needed for rechargeable batteries. This suggests that the copper foil surface undergoes microstructural changes after a short duration of cycling, likely due to stress- or strain-induced severe plastic deformation, as is often observed in copper when used as structural material.^[29] A recent theoretical study^[30] proposed that a stress gradient in the copper current collector can be built due to the stress associated with the lithium plating and stripping processes, whereby lithium diffuses into the copper current collector. Our study demonstrates that this stress gradient also induces microstructural changes in the top ~100 nm sub-surface region of the Cu current collector, where additional defects, such as dislocations and interfaces, may, in return, enhance lithium diffusion in the copper current collector with increasing cycles.

To investigate the lithium trapping in the copper current collector, APT was performed on the copper foils after one and three plating/stripping cycles (three datasets were obtained for each experiment). APT is a mass-spectrometry technique that allows for the reconstruction of 3D maps of atomic structures with near-atomic resolution from needle-shaped specimens.^[21] The reconstructed APT data take the form of 3D point clouds, where each colored dot represents an individual ion detected and elementally

identified. We can see in **Figure 3A**, a specimen prepared from the top surface of the copper foil after one cycle, that lithium (in blue) is unevenly distributed in the copper foil (in orange). When rotating the 3D reconstructed data, we can clearly distinguish that the lithium distribution resembles two planes, as shown in **Video S1** at around 5.97 s and 10.96 s. This result suggests that lithium is initially trapped at the grain boundaries inside the copper foil during cycling, as proposed by previous studies, but without direct experimental evidence.^[18,19,30,31]

Additionally, lithium trapping along the grain boundaries is rather non-uniform, as revealed by the cross-sectional atom maps presented in **Figure 3B** (a 5 nm slice in the grey-dashed region in **Figure 3A**). This might be induced by the fact that lithium likely diffuses into the grain boundaries driven by the stress gradient during plating (in addition to the force induced by the application of an electric field).^[30] Upon stripping, it appears that some lithium is unable to exit from the grain boundaries and pinned at, e.g., boundary junctions, as revealed by the ~3 nm lithium-rich cluster at the grain boundary junction observed in **Figure 3B**. The lithium concentration is up to 27.8 ± 0.5 at.% in the lithium-rich cluster at the boundary junction, as shown by the 1D concentration profile in **Figure 3F** (plotted by placing an analysis cylinder along the red arrow F in **Figure 3B**). The solubility of lithium in copper is about 12-16 at.% at room temperature according to the copper-lithium phase diagram.^[32,33] The considerable amounts of lithium at the boundary junction are likely arising from substantial amounts of vacancies and dislocations at the grain boundaries, especially at junctions, which alter the thermodynamic equilibrium as predicted by the phase diagram. In the top region of the grain boundaries, a ~4 nm lithium-rich cluster was observed as well, but with a concentration of 1-1.5 at.%, as revealed by the 1D concentration profile in **Figure 3G** (plotted along the arrow G in **Figure 3B**). In addition

to lithium trapped at the grain boundaries and junctions, some lithium is also trapped in the grain interior with a concentration of 0.04 ± 0.01 at.%, as summarized in **Table 1** and revealed in **Figure 3B**. Notably, the non-cycled copper foil also contains rather dilute amount of Li, i.e., 0.003 ± 0.001 at.% as impurities (see **Table 2**, summarized from two APT datasets of pristine copper foils), significantly lower, though, than the Li concentration in the grain interior after one and three cycles. This means that lithium diffuses not only along into/along the grain boundaries, but also into the grains. Grain boundary junctions containing more vacancies and dislocations can trap more lithium, though, making inward or outward diffusion during plating or stripping more difficult, which, in turn, leads to the formation of 3-4 nm-sized lithium-rich clusters at the grain boundaries and boundary junctions.

Besides lithium, oxygen-, carbon- and sulfur-containing complex molecular ions were also detected on the surface and inside the copper foil, such as Li_2O (**Figure 3C**), C, CH_3 and CH_4 (shown as CH_x in **Figure 3D**), CO and CO_2 (CO_x shown in **Figure 3D**), S and SO (SO_x , **Figure 3D**), O, CuO, CuOH, CuO_2 species (shown as O and Cu_xO_y in **Figure 3E**). These complex molecular ions are fragments from the electrolyte decomposition products during field evaporation of APT measurements (see the mass spectra in **Figure S4A**). Note that the thick electrolyte decomposition product layer was not detected by APT, likely due to fractures induced by field evaporation. Instead, the APT data in **Figure 3** show an elemental distribution from the copper surface on the top to the bulk (**Figure 3A-E**). CH_x , SO_x , CO_x molecular ions are mainly located on the surface. In contrast, O and Cu_xO_y molecular ions are distributed across top 40 nm surface regions, with slightly higher atomic oxygen concentration at the grain boundary (0.28 ± 0.05 at.% in **Table 1**) than in the grain interior (0.17 ± 0.01 in **Table 1**). Given the low oxygen content, oxygen is thought to diffuse into interstitial sites and vacancies

in the copper lattice rather than forming copper oxides. A previous *in situ* TEM study^[34] observed that impurity oxygen atoms can be embedded in the lithium crystals inside the graphene sheets during lithiation, and these oxygen atoms play a key role in trapping lithium in the graphene upon delithiation. Hence, we speculate that the oxygen trapped in the copper foil might also contribute to the irreversible lithium trapping, as also previously suggested by an NDP study.^[18]

After three plating/stripping cycles, lithium-rich regions are present not only on the surfaces but also ~70 nm below the copper surface (**Figure 4A,B**). The rotational 3D-APT reconstruction, shown in **Video S2**, unveils that lithium distributes in the form of linear-, planar- and particle-like features in the sub-surface region. This result aligns well with our observation in **Figure 2F** that the top 100 nm of the copper foil surface is nanocrystalline after three cycles. An increasingly large number of defects, i.e., vacancies, dislocations, and nanocrystal interfaces, are generated in the top 100 nm surface of the three-cycle copper foil, which likely trap lithium easily, leading to the formation of lithium-rich features in the sub-surface regions. Specifically, the sub-surface lithium-rich linear or planar features have a lithium concentration of 3.2 ± 0.1 at.%, as revealed by the 1D concentration profile shown in **Figure 4F** and **Table 1**. This is lower than the surface lithium concentration (~43 at.%), where lithium-containing electrolyte decomposition products are present. In addition, more lithium (0.08 ± 0.01 at.%) is found in the grain interior after three cycles compared to 0.04 ± 0.01 at.% of lithium after one cycle (cf. **Table 1**). This suggests that lithium can continuously diffuse into the copper lattice as the cycle number increases.

Also, in addition to Li_2O , CH_x , SO_x , CO_x , and $\text{O/Cu}_x\text{O}$ molecular ions, Li_2F and N-containing complex molecular ions are significantly enriched and clearly resolvable after three cycles in **Figure 4C-E** (see the mass spectra in **Figure S4B-C**). This

suggests that inner inorganic-rich electrolyte decomposition products were detected by APT, as indicated by the XPS results in **Figure S3**. Our APT data shows that Li_2O and Li_2F (**Figure 4C**) as well as CH_x , SO_x , CO_x , and N (**Figure 4D**) are distributed non-uniformly in the form of separate nanodomains. Li_2O , Li_2F , and CO_x are mainly detected in the top 10 nm surface regions (**Figure 4C,D**), whereas N and SO_x are distributed in the top ~20 nm region. In comparison, $\text{O}/\text{Cu}_x\text{O}_y$ molecular ions are present across the top 100 nm region (**Figure 4E**). The atomic O concentration reaches up to ~16 at.% locally in the top 30 nm surface region, as revealed in **Figure 4G**, which is significantly higher than that after one cycle (**Figure 3F**). This suggests that the copper foil surface is likely to be locally oxidized in the Cu foil sub-surface regions.

More interestingly, Li_2O (red dots in **Figure 4C**) and CH_x (brown dots in **Figure 4D**) molecular ions are also observed in the sub-surface ~70 nm region (**Figure 4C-E and Video S3**). We may speculate that carbon- and oxygen-containing electrolyte decomposition products might be unstable, further decomposing into oxygen and carbon and diffusing into the sub-surface. In comparison, F-, S- and N- containing electrolytes and decomposition products are relatively stable, leading to their absence in the sub-surface regions. The oxygen and carbon concentrations are ~2 at.% and ~1 at.% in the sub-surface areas. Intriguingly, oxygen and carbon are co-located with lithium-rich features in the sub-surface regions. This provokes us to speculate if oxygen and carbon, especially oxygen, further induce lithium trapping in copper. From the kinetic perspective, lithium diffusivity in a copper single crystal is $\sim 1.3 \times 10^{-20} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at room temperature,^[19] one order of magnitude lower than interstitial carbon diffusion ($\sim 4.2 \times 10^{-19} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, as extrapolated from a previous study^[35]) and two orders of magnitude lower than interstitial oxygen diffusion in copper

($\sim 1.2 \times 10^{-18} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$).^[36] When grain boundary diffusion is considered, lithium diffusivity in copper is significantly enhanced, albeit with significant variation in the literature (from $4 \times 10^{-17} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ to $\sim 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$).^[18,19,30] The diffusivity of oxygen and carbon along grain boundaries are thus expected to be faster than diffusivity via interstitials, still higher than that of lithium. This means that fast-diffusing oxygen and carbon could first arrive at defect sites before lithium in the sub-surface regions. Nonetheless, the diffusion of lithium, oxygen, and carbon in copper likely occurs *via* different processes: Lithium diffuses into copper upon plating, whereas oxygen and carbon, especially oxygen, might diffuse into copper during stripping. In fact, copper is easily oxidized at room temperature.^[37] Its affinity for oxygen and ability to lose electrons is enhanced at a positive potential upon stripping, during which oxygen might be trapped and stabilized preferentially at the defect sites, such as dislocations and nanocrystal interfaces generated in the copper sub-surface during cycling. Such oxygen and carbon segregation at defect sites may trap lithium and vice versa upon subsequent plating and stripping.

To further investigate the overall concentration in the copper foil, we summarized the contents of lithium and other elements from all APT datasets, including all regions, in **Table 2** (four datasets for one cycle and three datasets for three cycles). The overall lithium content increases from $0.27 \pm 0.01 \text{ at.}\%$ to $0.74 \pm 0.01 \text{ at.}\%$ as the cycle number increases from one to three cycles, similarly to the oxygen and carbon content from $0.22 \pm 0.01 \text{ at.}\%$ to $1.2 \pm 0.1 \text{ at.}\%$ and $0.05 \pm 0.02 \text{ at.}\%$ to $0.10 \pm 0.01 \text{ at.}\%$, respectively. Notably, the oxygen and carbon solubilities in copper are extremely low and have rarely been reported for room temperature.^[38] Thus, the creation of defects, dislocations, and interfaces in the copper foil surface and sub-surface region during plating and stripping is essential for providing the trapping sites for oxygen and carbon,

which jointly pin the lithium inward or outward diffusion during plating and stripping. Such lithium, oxygen, and carbon trapping likely degrades the copper current collector surface, potentially its electronic conductivity and leading to the commonly observed deterioration in battery cell performance. Collectively, the APT datasets indicate that cycling induces a defect-rich near-surface Cu region that traps Li along with unexpectedly high levels of O and C, pointing to a coupled electro-chemo-mechanical degradation mechanism.

3. Conclusion

In summary, our study unveils that lithium is trapped at the boundaries and their boundary junctions in the copper current collector after one plating/stripping cycle. The APT data confirm that lithium diffuses into the grain interior, grain boundaries, and boundary junctions, where it can be strongly pinned by forming 3-4 nm-sized lithium-rich clusters. As the cycle number increases, the copper current collector surface undergoes microstructural changes, with the grain size decreasing from a few micrometers after one cycle to tens of nanometers after three cycles. Such microstructural changes are accompanied by the formation of more defects, e.g., vacancies, dislocations, and interfaces, in the sub-surface region of the copper foil, fostering further lithium trapping. Additionally, more oxygen and carbon are observed in the sub-surface region along with lithium after three cycles. The presence of lithium, oxygen, and carbon in the sub-surface regions likely degrades the copper current collector, resulting in a gradual decrease in electronic conductivity and the overall performance as cycling proceeds. We may anticipate that these atomic-scale insights into the lithium loss and copper current-collector degradation will guide the development of innovative strategies to overcome the issues of commonly observed

(very) low coulombic efficiencies in zero-excess LMBs, thereby advancing the technology toward eventual commercialization.

4. Experimental Section

Electrolyte Preparation

The electrolyte was composed of a mixture of 1-butyl-1-methyl pyrrolidinium bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide (PYR₁₄FSI) and lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide salt (LiTFSI, 3M, battery grade) with a ratio of 8:2 (PYR₁₄FSI:LiTFSI). PYR₁₄FSI was synthesized according to the procedure reported by Montanino *et al.*^[39] and dried under vacuum (10^{-3} mbar) for 12 h at 70 °C. The lithium salt was dried under vacuum for 12 h at 120 °C. Subsequently, the ionic liquid and the salt were mixed in the given ratio to obtain the electrolyte, which was further dried under vacuum for 2 h at room temperature, for 6 h at 50 °C, and for 12 h at 80 °C. The same procedure was repeated using a turbomolecular pump (10^{-7} mbar) to reduce the water content to a few ppm. Afterwards, 5 wt.% fluoroethylene carbonate (FEC; Powerlyte) was added to the electrolyte according to a previous study in our lab, revealing a superior lithium stripping and plating behavior.^[22]

Cell Assembly

Pouch cells for the electrochemical tests were assembled in a dry room environment with a dew point of the incoming air of -70 °C. Lithium metal strips (thickness: 500 µm, Honjo Metal Co.) and copper foil (thickness: 40 µm, Welcos) were used as electrodes for the Li||Cu cells. Celgard® SV718 (thickness: 25 µm) and glass microfiber sheets (thickness: 260 µm, Whatman, GF/A) were used as separators, with Celgard facing the copper electrode and the glass microfiber sheet facing the lithium-metal electrode.

The separators were soaked with 100 μL of the electrolyte. To completely wet the separators and remove any residual air, the cells were placed under vacuum (10^{-3} mbar) for ca. 100 s. The cells were eventually sealed under vacuum. The active area for lithium plating and stripping was 0.785 cm^2 . The cell setup is shown in **Figure 1a**.

Electrochemical Characterization

Galvanostatic plating and stripping was conducted using a Maccor battery tester at $40\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. A total areal capacity of 1 mAh cm^{-2} was plated on the Cu electrode at a current density of 0.05 mA cm^{-2} within 20 h after a rest step of 12 h. The plating step was followed by stripping the lithium back to the lithium-metal electrode at the same current density for a maximum of 20 h or until the cut-off voltage of 0.3 V was reached. Either one or three full plating/stripping cycles were conducted.

STEM and APT characterization

For preparing the STEM and APT samples, the cycled pouch cells were opened in a Sylatech GB1500-E glovebox (O_2 and $\text{H}_2\text{O} < 0.1\text{ ppm}$), and the non-cycled and cycled electrodes were washed five times with 1,2-dimethoxyethane (DME; Sigma Aldrich) to remove any residual electrolyte. The top-down view SEM images were recorded using a FEI Helios G5 CX FIB/SEM at 2 and 10 kV. To prevent samples from oxidation and contamination during sample transfer, the Cu foils were transferred *via* a customized Ferrovac vacuum transfer suitcase. Afterward, the Cu foil surfaces were covered by a 120 nm thick Cr protective layer *via* physical vapor deposition coating using a Leica EM ACE600 sputter coater in order to prevent the sample surfaces from ion beam damage during specimen preparation by means of FIB/SEM. The STEM and APT specimens were prepared *via* standard lift-out procedures by using a FEI Helios G5

CX FIB/SEM. A 300 nm thick carbon film was deposited on the STEM samples by electron beam deposition prior to the lift-out process, followed by a 3 μm thick ion beam assisted carbon deposition. STEM images were recorded directly *via* FIB/SEM using a STEM detector at 30 kV. TKD was carried out with a JEOL JSM-7200F SEM at 30 kV with a sample tilt of 10 degree with a step size of 20 nm. The orientation contrast maps were acquired using an Oxford Instruments Symmetry camera controlled via AZtec software. The APT experiments were performed using a Cameca LEAP 5000 XR at a temperature of 65 K in laser mode. The APT specimens were transferred from FIB to APT using a Ferrovac Ultra High Vacuum Cryo Transfer Suitcase (UHVCTS, reaching a pressure of $<1 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar) to further minimize the oxidation of Cu APT needles. A laser pulse energy of 40 pJ, a pulse frequency of 125 kHz and a 0.4% detection rate were used as the experimental conditions during the APT acquisition. The reconstruction and APT data analysis were carried out using the AP Suite 6.3.3.55 software.

Depth-resolved X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis

The elemental composition and the chemical state of the elements at the (sub-)surface of the cycled Cu samples (after one plating/stripping cycle and after three cycles) was determined by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements using a Specs XPS system with a Phoibos 150 energy analyser. To avoid any surface contamination, the samples were transferred in inert gas atmosphere to the sample load lock of the XPS system. The measurements were done with monochromatized Al K_{α} radiation (300 W, 13 kV) and a pass energy of 30 eV at the analyser for the detail spectra. In order to get a depth profile of the elemental concentration, the topmost material was removed by successive Ar^{+} ion sputtering. Measurements were collected before

sputtering and after 10, 30, and 60 min of sputtering, with the latter being applied only for the sample subjected to three plating/stripping cycles. Charging effects at the surface were negligible and neutralization not necessary. The main C1s peak was set to 284.8 eV to compensate small peak shifts. The peak fit of the XPS results was done with CasaXPS, using Shirley-type backgrounds and Gaussian-Lorentzian (GL30) peak shapes. For the spectra in the Li 1s region, the peaks assigned to Li₂O and LiF were added at 53.8 and 55.6 eV, respectively. Their intensity was calculated based on the intensity of the corresponding peaks in the F 1s and O 1s regions, taking into account stoichiometry and relative sensitivity factors

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or the author.

Author Contributions

T.L. and D.B. conceptualized and supervised the project. C.L. performed APT and STEM measurements. C.L. and T.L. analyzed the APT data. O.A., Z.L. and M.S. prepared the electrolyte and cells, performed the electrochemical measurements, conducted the sample preparation. T.M. carried out the XPS measurements and analysis. A.K. performed the TKD measurements. All authors agreed on the contents and conclusion of the paper.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding authors upon reasonable request.

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Figure 1. Cell setup and galvanostatic lithium plating and stripping. (a) Illustration of lithium plating and stripping process on the copper current collector. (b) Schematic diagram showing the TEM lamella and APT specimens prepared in the center of the copper current collector after cleaning in DME and coating of a protective layer. (c,d) Voltage profiles recorded for the Li||Cu cells subjected to (c) one or (d) three plating/stripping cycles; the inset in (c) shows the three characteristic regimes of the initial plating step.

Figure 2. Top-down and cross-section view of the copper current collector after one and three plating/stripping cycles. (a,b) SEM micrographs showing the top-down view on the cleaned copper foil after (a) one and (b) three plating/stripping cycles. (c,d) Low-resolution STEM/high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) images showing the cross-section of the copper foil after (c) one and (d) three cycles, with insets

showing the magnified regions marked by the red-boxes in (c) and (d). The TEM lamellae prepared from the red-box regions in a and b, respectively. (e,f) Orientation contrast maps recorded by transmission Kikuchi diffraction of the cross-section of the copper foil after (e) one and (f) three plating/stripping cycles (from the same TEM lamellae in (c) and (d), respectively). (g,h) Magnified view of the STEM/dark-field images of the cross-section of the copper current collector after one and three plating/stripping cycles from the dashed red box in (c) and (d), respectively.

Figure 3. Detection of lithium in the copper current collector after one plating/stripping cycle. (a) 3D-APT reconstructed data revealing the trapping of lithium in the grain boundaries present in the copper foil. (b-e) Atom maps from the grey dashed region in (a), displaying the distribution of Li, Li_2O , $\text{CH}_x/\text{SO}_x/\text{CO}_x$, and O-containing molecular ions (from left to right). (f) 1D Concentration profiles plotted along the grain boundary and boundary junction shown in (b) marked f. (g) 1D Concentration profiles from the top 15 nm region of (f) marked G in (b).

Figure 4. Detection of lithium in the copper current collector after three plating/stripping cycles. (a) 3D-APT reconstructed data showing the presence of Li on the surface and ~60 nm region below the surface. (b-e) Atom maps from the grey dashed region in (a) revealing the distribution of Li, $\text{Li}_2\text{O}/\text{Li}_2\text{F}$, $\text{CH}_x/\text{SO}_x/\text{CO}_x/\text{N}$ and O-containing molecular ions (from left to right). (f) 1D Concentration profile plotted along the arrow in (a) showing only the lithium and copper content. (g) The same 1D concentration profiles as in (f), but showing the atomic O, F, S, C, and N content.

Table 1. Composition in different regions of the copper foil after one and three plating/stripping cycles.

Element	1 cycle			3 cycles		
	Grain interior	Li-rich cluster at boundary junctions	Surface regions	Grain interior	Surface Li-rich regions	Bottom Li-rich regions
Li	0.04 ± 0.01	27.8 ± 0.5	0.33 ± 0.02	0.08 ± 0.01	42.9 ± 0.5	3.2 ± 0.1
Cu	99.8 ± 0.1	71.9 ± 0.8	98.7 ± 0.4	98.7 ± 0.1	48.4 ± 0.5	95.2 ± 0.4
O	0.17 ± 0.01	0.28 ± 0.05	0.72 ± 0.03	1.1 ± 0.1	4.6 ± 0.2	1.10 ± 0.04
C	0.01 ± 0.01	0.05 ± 0.02	0.10 ± 0.01	0.02 ± 0.01	0.35 ± 0.04	0.49 ± 0.03
N	-	-	-	0.02 ± 0.01	0.12 ± 0.03	0.02 ± 0.01
S	0.01 ± 0.01	-	0.14 ± 0.01	0.07 ± 0.01	0.68 ± 0.06	0.06 ± 0.01
F	-	-	-	0.02 ± 0.01	3.0 ± 0.1	-

Table 2. Elemental compositions inside the copper current collector in the pristine state (two datasets), after one (four datasets), and after three cycles (four datasets) including all regions.

Element	Pristine Cu	1 cycle	3 cycles
Li	0.003 ± 0.001	0.27 ± 0.01	0.74 ± 0.01
Cu	99.9 ± 0.1	99.5 ± 0.1	97.8 ± 0.1
O	0.09 ± 0.01	0.22 ± 0.01	1.2 ± 0.1
C	0.01 ± 0.01	0.02 ± 0.01	0.14 ± 0.01
N	-	-	0.03 ± 0.01
S	0.01 ± 0.01	0.02 ± 0.01	0.09 ± 0.01
F	-	-	0.04 ± 0.01